

Review Article

The model of a university city and an urban university

Aleksandr Levintov

Independent Researcher, Russia

Introduction

I have been very lucky in my life - I have had the opportunity to observe, work and live in many, very different universities, including some that I do not want to remember or have nothing to remember. Many universities I know are located in large cities: Moscow State University and up to fifty other Moscow universities, Charles University in Prague, Sorbonne in Paris, USLA in Los Angeles, universities in San Francisco and San Diego, Portland, Madrid and Barcelona, Habana, Munich, Togliatti, Simferopol, Kaliningrad, Vilnius, Riga, Tyumen, Tomsk, Voronezh, Irkutsk - we are not talking about them here. Much nicer and more expressive are the universities in the smaller cities I've been to: Berkeley, Palo Alto (Stanford University), Chico, San Juan Obispo, Santa Cruz, Monterey, Hayward, Santa Barbara, Davis - in California, the universities of Passau and Ingolstadt (Bavaria), the University of Tartu in Estonia, Novosibirsk University in Akademgorodok, as well as the famous for literature and film Uppsala (Sweden), Cambridge, Oxford, Eton (England), Ivy League universities (Yale, Harvard, Princeton, Brown, Pennsylvania, Columbia, Cornell and Dartmouth Colleges) and, in addition, the American universities of Potsdam, Syracuse and Kalamazoo.

These universities are not only charming in appearance, but also form the basis of university education and science on a global scale: after all, science tends to be secluded and isolated, a contrast to the big cities. The war of town contra gown, the war of town against gown, which emerged during the Hundred Years' War, strictly speaking, continues because of the singularity of science and university education.

On the basis of this life and book experience, I allowed myself to model a generalized "gentleman's set" of the university town and the university campus proper. What emerged was a fairly simple morphological set with occasional comments, mostly necessary.

Campus

Usually a vast tract of land for a university or college is provided or sold by a city not in the center of the city, more often even on the outskirts, since the university is not valued at all as a tax-paying asset. In many cases, the center of the city begins to shift to the university campus, or a second important center of urban activity emerges here. Almost always, the campus is an area "for growth", with reserves for growth and even expansion.

Education and science

These are the two main university activities, while architecturally and

Corresponding author

Aleksandr Levintov. PhD (Geography), Independent Researcher. Russia

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plan-wise they are quite distinct from each other: the classrooms are of several sizes, the science and engineering spaces are strictly functional. What is common is the presence of conference spaces, recreational and recreational areas, and places of retreat.

Business

Strictly speaking, education and science are businesses, but universities also have technical businesses, such as technology parks, business centers, co-working spaces, meeting rooms and buildings.

Support services (printing house, library, archives, collections)

The set of these services is quite individualized, up to industrial and agribusinesses.

Relaxation and recreation (theater, sports, fitness, health care)

This segment is generally open-ended and available not only to campus residents but also to city dwellers.

Dormitory and Sex

Students prefer to live in dormitories on campus or in close proximity to the university, they are young and sexually more than active: an aura of amorosness hovers over every university. Professors, academics, administrative and service staff prefer public, private or rented accommodation outside the university and away from the noisy 24/7 student population.

Trade and catering

On a strict scale and in accordance with the university's facilities and needs.

Entertainment and amusement

And this area more often has opportunities to attract and townspeople, mainly for commercial purposes.

Administration

Located in modest buildings and facilities, but with logistics as accessible as possible.

Local government

The most striking and expressive architectural symbol of self-government is the aula, the idea of which dates back to the traditions of the Roman Forum and the Athenian Agora. The aula is also a symbol of unity between students and professors.

Protection of people, facilities and information (trade secrets)

These are not the idlers typical of Russia, but very busy and functionally loaded services.

Transportation, communication and other means of moving people and information

We are talking about parking lots and parking lots, loading and unloading docks and overpasses, electric cars, bicycles, boards, skis, segregated paths, primarily pedestrian paths, gas stations, etc.

Church

The task of embracing all faiths is not before the university, even with the most frenzied global popularity and demand.

Club spaces

Club spaces are numerous, diverse and mobile, as they arise and form spontaneously. All these smokers, nooks, crannies and pools have controlled entrances and uncontrolled exits.

Public spaces

There is always room for public events, rallies, parades, marches, celebrations and protests.

Park and retreat areas

Even in the tightest of cities, university campuses have parks and park areas, places of solitude and deep solitude, without this a university cannot truly exist.

Urban environment

The closer you get to the university, the brighter, more diverse and more democratic the urban life. Democracy is not about majority rule, but about maximizing the encouragement of minorities.

Settlement

The more status professors, scientists and managers have, the more remote from campus and expensive their housing is, all other things being equal.

Commerce and Dining

Only the nearest drinking and shopping outlets, traditionally favored by various university groups and communities, are oriented toward the university. The fate of people, the university, the city, the nation, and humanity is often decided here.

Schools, courses, seminars

These structures also cling to the university, although they may be com-

pletely unrelated to them, or they may be in irreconcilable opposition and an alternative. These are often child-oriented: art schools, music schools, dance schools, etc.

Enlightenment

Enlightenment activities are also noticeably oriented towards proximity to the university, the true crucible of enlightenment, culture and education.

Silver University

In particular, adult schools, various cutting and sewing, computer, sculpting, puppetry, political discussion, travel, health, cooking, etc. circles, favorite activities of retirees, swirl in and around the university.

Clubs

Many urban clubs are molded around universities casually or out of habit, emphasizing by their presence the intellectual importance of the university, its metropolitanity relative to the city.

Auxiliary services

Do not have such a clear spatial orientation, not even dry cleaners and laundries.

Church and religious organizations

All denominations hang around universities, either as sponsors or as petitioners.

Cultural infrastructure

Strives to be accessible to the university.

Engineering infrastructure

Almost completely indifferent to the university, as it is primarily urban.

Repair services

Also poorly oriented towards the university.

Police

Most universities prohibit the army and police from appearing at the university (except in special cases), so the police appear near the university with the same frequency as in the entire city.

Urban and external transportation and communications

Well, this shuns universities altogether.

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